

VARAXSHA - BUXOROXUDOTLAR QARARGOHI

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o'qituvchisi

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Tayanch so'zlar: yodgorlik, dashti urganji , rajfandum , qo'shminora merosi,

Annotatsiya Buxoro hududidagi arxeologik topilmalar haqida so'z yuritilganda ,eng mashxurlaridan biri Varaxsha yodgorligi yodimizda tushadi.bu maqolada yodgorlikning madaniy me'rosi va topilmalarining qisqacha sharhlari mujassamlashtirilgan.

Аннотация Когда мы говорим об археологических находках в Бухарской области, на ум приходит одна из самых известных – памятник Варахша. В данной статье содержится краткий обзор культурного наследия памятника и находок.

Annotation When we talk about the archaeological finds in the Bukhara region, one of the most famous ones, the Varakhsha monument, comes to mind. This article contains a brief overview of the cultural heritage of the monument and the findings.

VARAXSHA — Qadimgi shahar xarobasi. Buxorodan 40 km shimoli-g'arbda, Dashti Urganji ko'lining qadimgi Ranjfundun vohasida joylashgan. Varaxsha maydoni 9 ga va balandligi 10-20 metrli ulkan tepa shaklida saqlangan.

Arxeologik qazishmalardan ma'lum bo'lishicha, Varaxsha mil. avv. II asrda bir-biriga tutashgan bir nechta istehkomli qishloqlar tarzida qad ko'targan. Varaxsha xarobalarining shimoli-g'arbida qadimgi qo'rg'onlardan birining tashqi devori hamda yarim doira shaklidagi burji (ichki sahni 4,5x5 m) kavlab o'rganilgan.

Devor (qalinligi 1,8-1,9 m) xom g'ishtdan (hajmi 37x41x10 sm) qurilgan.

Devor va burjlarida paykonsimon nishon tuynuklari (ichki tomoni 38-40 sm, tashqarisi 75-80 sm, kengligi 20-22 sm) ochilgan.

Mil. avv. II-I asrlarda va milodiy I-II asrlarda Varaxsha va uning atrofida madaniy hayot gullagan. III-IV asrlarda Varaxsha tanazzulga yuz tutgan.

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V asrda Varaxsha yana tiklanib Buxoroning qadimgi hukmdorlari — buxorxudotlarning qarorgohiga aylangan. Shu davrda Varaxsha mustahkam devor bilan o'ralgan, uning janubiy qismida ark qurilgan.

VIII-X asrlarda ayniqsa obod bo'lgan. Varaxsha va uning atroflari o'n ikki kanal bilan sug'orilib, Rajfandun vohasidagi eng yirik va markaziy qal'alardan biriga aylangan. Buxoro va Xorazm oralig'idagi karvon yo'li Varaxsha orqali o'tgan (Istaxriy va Ibn Havqal ma'lumotlari). Buxorxudotlar qarorgohi qilinishi bilan Varaxsha yirik shaharga aylangan. Har o'n besh kunda Varaxshada bir kunlik, yil oxirida 20 kunlik bozor sayli (navro'zi kashovarzon, ya'ni dehqonlar yangi yili) o'tkazilgan (Narshaxiy). Buxorxudotlar qarorgohi qilinishi bilan Varaxsha yirik shaharga aylangan. XI-XII asrlarda uning hududi eniga 6 km dan ziyod bo'lgan.

XII asrda Varaxsha vohasidagi hayot to'satdan noma'lum sabablarga ko'ra to'xtab qolgan.

1949-1954-yillarda Varaxsha tarixi va me'morchiligi o'rganildi.

Kvadrat shakldagi yirik xom g'ishtlardan qo'shminora tarzida o'rab chiqilgan tagkursi (balandligi 15 m) larning biriga podsho saroyi va ikkinchisiga soqchixonali darvozaxona bino qilingan.

Arkning sharqiy qismida tomi ravoqsimon gumbaz tarzida yopilgan uzun yo'laksimon (navkarxona va darvozaxona) xonalar mavjud bo'lgan.

Arkning markazida janubiy tomoni mudofaa devoriga yondoshgan Varaxsha hukmdorining saroyi joylashgan.

U Sharqiy (11,5 x 17 m) va G'arbiy (6,6x7,25 m) mehmonxona hamda Qizil xona (zal) (8,5x12 m) lardan iborat bo'lgan. Saroy g'arb tomonidan 3 ravoqli ganchkori ustunlar o'rnatilgan hashamatli peshayvon bilan o'ralgan.

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Ayvon ravoqlarining ustunlari va toqilari ganchkori qabartma tasvirlar hamda turli xil girihlar bilan bezatilgan. Saroyning Qizil xona va Sharqiy mehmonxonalari to'la kavlab ochilgan. Xona devorlari mayda somonli loy suvoq ustidan yupqa ganch suvoq qilinib, devoriy rasmlar qizil, sariq, kulrang, qora, zangori, pushti va jigarrang bo'yoqlar bilan bezatilgan.

Ularda turli xil manzaralar, fil mingan shahzoda va chokarlarning old va ortdan chovut solgan qoplonlar bilan olishuvi; qayrilib nishonga kamondan o'q uzayotgan ot ustidagi chavandoz, qanotli tuya shaklidagi oltin taxtda o'tirgan hukmdor tasvirlangan. Sharqiy mehmonxona devorida tiz cho'kib, qo'lida qadah tutgan malika, belida shamshir, bir qo'lida qisqich ushlagan podshoh, o'rtada vazasimon otashgohda yonib turgan muqaddas olov-azarxurro, otashgohdan

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o'ngda beliga xanjar taqilgan shahzodaning tiz cho'kib ibodat qilayotgan tasviri yoki sovut va dubulg'a kiygan, qo'llarida nayza, qalqon ushlagan suvoriylarning jang qilayotgan, shuningdek butazor, to'qay ichidagi ov manzarasi kabi tasvirlar ayniqsa diqqatga sazovordir.

Arxeologik topilmalardan aniqlanishicha, janubiy xonalarning ikkinchi qavatidagi xona ganchkori naqshlar bilan bezatilgan ekan.

Ko'plab topilgan qabartma ganchkori naqshlar orasida hovuzda suzib yurgan baliqlar, yerlkasidan o'q yegan arxar, yelib borayotgan jayran, bedanalar, ayol boshli baxt qushi — Humo, hamlaga tayyorlanayotgan ajdarho, taqimiga sadoq bog'lagan suvoriy hamda ko'pdan ko'p ayollarning bosh qismlari bilan bir qatorda turli xil islomiy va girih parchalari uchraydi

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